

Non-biting midge (Diptera: Chironomidae) diversity in the University of the Philippines Diliman, Quezon City including the description and DNA barcoding of a new species *Kiefferulus dilimanensis* sp. nov. and four new records

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Abstract

Urban biodiversity studies often emphasize disease vectors and economically important insects, leaving ecologically significant groups underexplored. In the Philippines, urban development has degraded aquatic systems, with biomonitoring revealing pollution-tolerant taxa. The family Chironomidae Newman, 1834, among the most pollution-tolerant aquatic insects, remains taxonomically understudied in tropical Asia. This study surveyed Chironomidae in the University of the Philippines Diliman, one of the remaining green spaces in Metro Manila. One new species, *Kiefferulus dilimanensis* sp. nov., and four new records, *K. calligaster* (Kieffer, 1911), *Chironomus circumdatus* (Kieffer, 1916), *C. crassiforceps* Kieffer, 1916, and *C. flaviplumus* Tokunaga, 1940, were identified. Diagnostic traits, particularly of the male hypopygium, were illustrated and incorporated into a local dichotomous key. Mitochondrial COI (mtCOI) (658 bp) analysis supported morphological delineations: *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. formed a distinct clade (bootstrap = 99) with 9.00–9.43% K2P divergence from *K. tainanus* (Kieffer, 1912) and *K. barbatitarsis* (Kieffer, 1911), exceeding typical intraspecific thresholds (<3%). Philippine *K. calligaster* clustered with Asian conspecifics (1.49–2.83% divergence), while *C. circumdatus* and *C. flaviplumus* (Type C) showed low divergences ($\leq 1.12\%$), confirming conspecificity. *C. crassiforceps* exhibited higher divergence (3.02–7.40%), suggesting cryptic diversity. This study provides the first COI barcodes for Philippine Chironomidae and underscores the role of integrative taxonomy in revealing hidden biodiversity within tropical urban ecosystems.

Key words: Chironomidae, *Kiefferulus dilimanensis*, new species, new record, Philippines, UP Diliman

Introduction

Urban expansion profoundly affects local biodiversity, yet studies on urban insects, particularly those in fragmented greenspaces remains understudied due to a historical focus on economically important species (Collins *et al.*, 2024). In the Philippines, only a few insect taxonomic studies exist in urban areas such as those on mosquitoes (Mistica *et al.*, 2019), ants (Pag-ong *et al.*, 2023), butterflies (Nacua *et al.*, 2020; Itliong *et al.*, 2024), and dragonflies (Banaybanay, 2024), while many other groups remain undocumented or understudied. Urban environments are challenged by dense human populations, pollution, and the conversion of natural habitats into built-up areas (Vallejo *et al.*, 2009), which consequently affect ecosystem services (Li *et al.*, 2023). Philippine cities have been largely overlooked as priorities for biodiversity conservation (Vallejo *et al.*, 2009). Metro Manila is one of the world's largest urban centers with a population of over 13 million people (PSA, 2020). The replacement of natural habitats by concrete infrastructure is evident in many cities of Metro Manila. Amid this urban sprawl, the University of the Philippines Diliman (UP Diliman) stands out as one of the last significant green spaces in Metro Manila. Biodiversity research in the campus has so far focused on more visible fauna such as reptiles, birds, amphibians, and mammals (Ong *et al.*, 1999; Vallejo Jr. *et al.*, 2008, 2009; Pasumbal *et al.*, 2022). Urban stream ecosystems within the campus are not immune to development impacts: an

assessment by Magbanua *et al.* (2019) revealed that the benthic macroinvertebrate communities in UP Diliman's streams are dominated by pollution-tolerant family Chironomidae Newman, 1834, specifically the genera *Chironomus* Meigen, 1803, *Cricotopus* van der Wulp, 1874, and *Thienemanniomyia* Fittkau, 1957, suggesting impaired water quality.

Given this context, UP Diliman offers an opportunity to explore the lesser-studied insect fauna of urban habitats particularly semi-aquatic insects like chironomids that are widely known bioindicators of environmental health. Chironomids are cosmopolitan (Zhang *et al.*, 2024) in distribution including Antarctica (Da Silva and Farrell, 2017), with approximately 7,300 species worldwide (Pape *et al.*, 2011). Chironomid habitats range from the most pristine environments to highly polluted areas, and from stagnant to rapidly flowing waters, as well as in both freshwater and saline environments (Sæther and Ekrem, 2003; Wade *et al.*, 2004). Chironomid larvae abundance, diversity, pollution tolerance, limited mobility, and ease of sampling make them established indicators for lentic and lotic ecosystems (Rosenberg, 1992; Rosenberg and Resh, 1993; Wade *et al.*, 2004; Ferrington *et al.*, 2008; Karima, 2021). Unlike larvae, chironomid adults are short-lived with limited aerial dispersal (Da Silva and Farrell, 2017). Chironomidae are biological bridges as they carry in-Stream Energy: transferring energy and nutrients from stream ecosystems where they develop to the terrestrial landscape and become part of other food webs, thereby integrating aquatic and terrestrial ecological processes (Hayford *et al.*, 2018).

Despite the importance of these organisms, taxonomic knowledge is relatively limited in the oriental region compared to the Holarctic and Afrotropical regions (Ashe *et al.*, 1987). In Southeast Asia, information on species diversity is particularly scarce (Al-Shami *et al.*, 2009; Pramual *et al.*, 2016), and in the Philippines only 12 species have been recorded (Baltazar, 1990), with no subsequent taxonomic studies or records. Chironomids in their larval form are only part of studies regarding water quality assessments of Philippine rivers, and they are only identified up to genus level (*e.g.*, Magbanua *et al.*, 2019 and 2023; Peralta *et al.*, 2019; Jolejole *et al.*, 2021). Larval identifications are typically limited to the genus level as species-level resolution generally requires examination of adult male genitalia, which cannot be assessed in larvae (Failla *et al.*, 2015; Kang *et al.*, 2022a; Cranston and Tang, 2024). Consequently, the Philippines still lacks an updated species inventory and taxonomic baseline for Chironomidae, highlighting UP Diliman as a strategic site to initiate such research.

Traditional chironomid taxonomy is complicated by pronounced intraspecific variation and the existence of cryptic species complexes (Cranston and Edward, 1999). Cytotaxonomic methods particularly larval polytene-chromosome banding (Keyl and Keyl, 1959; Martin, 1963; Blaylock, 1966; Kuvangkadilok, 1985; Michailova, 1989; Kumar and Gupta, 1990; Butler *et al.*, 1999; Sella *et al.*, 2004; Kiknadze *et al.*, 2008) have clarified some complexes, but they demand specialist expertise and are restricted to certain larval instars (Pramual *et al.*, 2016). Because diagnostic adult characters are absent in larvae, material collected for bioassessment must still be linked back to an adult-based name (Ekrem *et al.* 2007).

To bridge this gap, DNA barcoding using the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) gene (Hebert *et al.*, 2003) has become a powerful adjunct to morphology (Pramual *et al.*, 2016; Martin, 2020; Kang *et al.*, 2022a, 2022b). Numerous studies across biogeographic regions show that barcodes reliably discriminate most chironomid species and rapidly flag hidden diversity (Sharley *et al.*, 2004; Carew *et al.*, 2005, 2007; Pfenninger *et al.*, 2007; Al-Shami *et al.*, 2009; Carew and Hoffmann, 2015; Kang *et al.*, 2022a, 2022b). Although recent or ongoing hybridization can blur species boundaries in a few groups (Guryev and Blinov, 2002; Proulx *et al.*, 2013), overall success rates remain high, enabling rapid diversity assessments, robust species-distribution mapping, and more precise use of Chironomidae as freshwater bioindicators (Sharley *et al.*, 2004). Barcoding also serves a quality-control function: database queries quickly expose misidentified vouchers or incongruent sequence clusters, ensuring that barcode libraries remain taxonomically coherent (Pramual *et al.*, 2016).

Therefore, this baseline taxonomic study of Chironomidae of UP Diliman aims to identify adult Chironomidae species collected along the waterway banks of UP Diliman using an integrative taxonomic approach that combined morphological examination and mitochondrial COI (mtCOI) DNA barcoding. Additionally, a preliminary dichotomous key was developed to facilitate local species identification. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the baseline taxonomic knowledge of Philippine Chironomidae, enhance representation in regional and global barcode reference libraries, and support future ecological and biomonitoring efforts in urban freshwater environments.

Materials and methods

Sampling site and collection method

The University of the Philippines Diliman (UP Diliman) is situated in Quezon City (14° 38' N, 121° 2' E) with a vast area of 493 ha which functions as a community with various academic, residential, and commercial facilities (**Fig. 1**). The climate of Quezon City is classified as tropical monsoonal, with a distinct dry season from November to April and a wet season from May to October (PAGASA, 2025).

Figure 1. Satellite view of UP Diliman; Actual photos of sampling sites: **B.** UP Lagoon and **C.** University Avenue Waterways

Adult chironomid samples were collected from two sampling sites within the University of the Philippines Diliman campus using Black Light Traps (BLT) and White Light Traps (WLT) operated between 6pm and 9pm. BLTs emit ultraviolet (UV) light, which is highly attractive to many nocturnal Diptera, whereas WLTs emit broad-spectrum visible light that attracts a wider range of flying insects. Adult chironomids are positively phototactic; thus, light traps were employed to attract flying individuals during evening activity periods (Pallottini *et al.*, 2024). On March 18, 2024, both BLT and WLT were deployed along the cemented waterway bank of the UP Diliman Lagoon, which is predominantly lined with mahogany trees. On March 19, 2024, both trap types were again utilized along the waterway bank adjacent to University Avenue, characterized by dense shrub cover and canopy shade from Fabaceae trees.

Male specimens suitable for species-level identification were obtained from both BLT and WLT during these two sampling dates. A subsequent sampling at the Lagoon site was conducted on May 23, 2024, during which both BLT and WLT were deployed, however, the BLT collection consisted predominantly of female specimens, which were not suitable for species-level identification. Consequently, only male specimens obtained from the WLT on this date were included in the taxonomic analysis. As the study aimed primarily at taxonomic inventory rather than quantitative abundance comparison, this methodological difference is not expected to have influenced species documentation. All collected specimens were preserved in 95% technical-grade ethyl alcohol (Just-In-One Marketing, Quezon City, Philippines), which was used consistently throughout the study.

Sorting, dissection, and slide mounting

Samples were initially sorted and identified in the Wetland and Terrestrial-linked Ecosystems Research Laboratory (WATER Lab) in the Institute of Biology, UP Diliman. Samples were then brought to Sahmyook University in Seoul, South Korea for slide mounting, picture taking, and molecular work. The antennae, head, wings, abdomen, and hypopygium of the adult chironomids were dissected using fine needles or dissecting forceps under a stereomicroscope (Olympus SZ, Japan) and then mounted on permanent slides with Euparal medium. The slides were subjected to drying for 2–4 days. Some replicates were maintained or wet-preserved in 95% ethanol. Morphology of the hypopygium with the male genitalia were illustrated first, on a paper with the aid of a light box which was later scanned for tracing in Adobe Illustrator version 25.3 (64-bit) (Adobe Inc., San Jose, CA, USA) for digitization. Morphological identification followed available keys, checklists, original descriptions, and other references such as those of Tokunaga (1964), Sasa (1978, 1979, 1989), and Sasa and Hasegawa (1983), Sasa and Suzuki (2001), Sasa and Kikuchi (1995), Wiederholm (1989), Papp and Darvas (1998), Spies and Sæther (2004), Langton and Pinder (2007), and Martin (2020).

Morphological measurements

After the molecular work in South Korea, the slide-mounted or wet-preserved specimens were transported back to the WATER Lab, UP Diliman and were examined under a Motic digital compound microscope (Moticam 580) for morphological measurements, following the terminology and methods of Sasa (1995). All measurements are expressed in micrometers (μm). Standard ratios, including antennal ratio (AR), palpal ratio (PR), fore leg ratio (fLR), mid leg ratio (mLR), hind leg ratio (hLR), fore tarsal-tibial ratio (fTR), venarum ratio (VR), radius ratio (RR), and the R/Cu ratio (the horizontal distance between the Arcus and tip of R_{4+5} divided by that between the Arcus and tip of Cu_1), were calculated to facilitate comparisons across specimens. Maxillary palp ratios were computed relative to the smallest segment of each palp. Descriptions were based on the measured structures of the head, thorax, wings, legs, and abdomen, with values presented as means and observed ranges. Measurements of leg segments, including femur (Fe), tibia (Ti), and tarsomeres 1–5 (Ta_1 – Ta_5), and corresponding ratios are summarized in **Tables 1–5**.

Molecular assessment

DNA extraction, amplification, and sequencing

Prior to DNA extraction, the remaining structures of the dissected samples were subjected to 95% ethanol, particularly the thoracic pre-episternum, from which the total genomic DNA was extracted using DNeasy Blood and Tissue Kit of Qiagen from Germany. DNA extraction was done following the method of Kang *et al.* (2022b). To amplify a partial sequence of the mtCOI (658bp) gene, a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was conducted using TaKaRa Ex Taq (Takara Bio, Shiga, Japan) with the universal primer sets (LCO1490: 5'-GGT CAA CAA ATC ATA AAG ATA TTG G-3', HCO2198: 5'-TAA ACT TCA

GGG TGA CCA AAA AAT CA-3') (Folmer *et al.*, 1994). The PCR was prepared in a total volume of 50 μL consisting of 33.75 μL of distilled water, 5 μL of 10X Ex Taq buffer, 4 μL of dNTP Mixture (2.5 mM each), 2 μL of each primer, 0.25 μL of TaKaRa Ex Taq, and 3 μL of genomic DNA template. The PCR conditions were as follows: an initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 s, annealing at 50°C for 30 s, extension at 72°C for 40 s, and a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. The amplified PCR products were isolated on a 1% agarose gel and sequencing of the partial mtCOI gene was performed bidirectionally using an ABI PRISM 3700 DNA analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA).

Sequence analysis and tree building

Philippine chironomid species sequences available from BOLD and GenBank were downloaded and verified. For representation, one to four sequences available per country were included, with lengths ranging from 532–685 base pairs. Sequence availability differed between databases: some COI sequences were deposited only in GenBank, some only in BOLD, and others in both (**Table 6**). The Philippine chironomid sequences (eight sequences), together with those from other countries available in the libraries (98 sequences), were aligned using the ClustalW algorithm in MEGA version 11.0 (Tamura *et al.*, 2013), yielding a final alignment of 658 base pairs. The best-fitting substitution model, General Time Reversible with Gamma distribution and Invariant sites (GTR+G+I), was identified in MEGA and subsequently applied to construct a maximum likelihood (ML) tree. Bootstrap analysis with 1,000 replicates was performed to assess nodal support. Intraspecific and interspecific sequence divergences were measured based on the Kimura 2-parameter (K2P) distance model (Kimura, 1980).

Depository

The holotype of *Kiefferulus dilimanensis* sp. nov. and one paratype is deposited at the National Museum of Natural History, Manila, Philippines (NMP). All other types and the specimens of newly recorded species are deposited in UP Diliman Institute of Biology Invertebrate Museum (UPDIM). All sequences were submitted to GenBank.

Results

Morphological Identification

Approximately 50 chironomid individuals were collected opportunistically and sorted, with only male specimens included in the morphological and molecular analysis due to the taxonomic significance of male genitalia in species-level identification. Fourteen individuals were examined for morphological description, while only eight individuals processed for DNA barcoding. Detailed examination of the hypopygium, the terminal abdominal segment housing the male genitalia, resulted in the identification of five distinct species assigned to two genera: *Kiefferulus* (two species) and *Chironomus* (three species). The hypopygia exhibited clear and consistent morphological differences within the five species, enabling confident genus- and species-level classification. These findings underscore the diagnostic value of male genital structures in chironomid taxonomy. The identity of the species was confirmed using mtCOI sequence analysis.

The 1990 checklist of Philippine Chironomidae compiled by Dr. Clare H. Baltazar, listing 12 species, was reviewed and cross-referenced with relevant literature. Some species were noted as “Unplaced Species” by Dr. Baltazar without direct context, but this could mean taxonomic uncertainty. The following are the 12 Chironomidae species recorded by Baltazar (1990):

A. Subfamily Chironominae

1. *Dicrotendipes niveicauda* Kieffer, 1921
 - a. Synonym: *Limnochironomus niveicauda* Kieffer, 1921
2. *Glyptotendipes philippinarum* Kieffer, 1921 or
 - a. Synonym: *Phytochironomus philippinarum* Kieffer, 1921
 - b. considered as nomen dubium (Spies & Sæther, 2004)
3. *Polypedilum stictopterus* Kieffer, 1921
 - a. Synonym: *Microtendipes stictopterus* Kieffer, 1921
4. *Xenochironomus trochanteratus* Thomson, 1869
 - a. Synonym: *Chironomus trochanteratus* Thomson, 1869
5. Unplaced species of Chironomini: *Kribiodoxa pulchripennis* Kieffer, 1921

B. Subfamily Orthoclaadiinae (Unplaced)

1. *Camptocladius dichromus* Edwards, 1929 - This was originally described under the genus *Camptocladius*. Delfinado & Hardy (1971) subsequently listed the species under the combination *Smittia dichromus* (Edwards) in their catalogue of Philippine Diptera type specimens. The “Unplaced” designation in Baltazar (1990) reflects checklist organization rather than explicit taxonomic uncertainty. The species remains within Subfamily Orthoclaadiinae, although its generic placement has varied historically in the literature.

C. Subfamily Tanypodinae

1. *Ablabesmyia moniliformis* Fittkau, 1962
2. *Clinotanypus atromarginatus* Edwards, 1929
3. *Clinotanypus paivai* Kieffer, 1910
 - a. Synonym: *Procladius paivai* Kieffer, 1910
4. *Clinotanypus philippinensis* Kieffer, 1921
 - a. Synonym: *Procladius philippinensis* Kieffer, 1921
5. *Clinotanypus variegatus* Kieffer, 1926
6. Unplaced species of Tanypodinae: *Zavrelimyia manilensis* Schiner, 1968
 - a. Synonym: *Tanypus manilensis* Schiner, 1968

The Philippines started having chironomid records in 1921 as initiated by Kieffer (Kieffer, 1921; Baltazar, 1986). In this list of Baltazar (1990), six species were seen in Kieffer’s book in 1921 (*Dicrotendipes niveicauda*, *Glyptotendipes philippinarum*, *Polypedilum stictopterus*, *Kribiodoxa pulchripennis*, *Clinotanypus philippinensis*, and *Ablabesmyia moniliformis* (*A. moniliformis* was listed as *Tanypus monilis* in Kieffer’s book). It is currently not clear who discovered the rest of the species in the list but Baltazar (1990) stated that Kieffer monopolized chironomids in the country and his publication is the only reference at that time (Baltazar, 1986) so it is more likely that the remaining species were also his discoveries. None of the five species identified from UP Diliman matched or were found to be synonymous with the species listed in Baltazar’s compilation. The five species are good representatives of the genera *Kiefferulus* Goetghebuer, 1922 and *Chironomus* Meigen, 1803 and are distinct from those listed by Baltazar, 1990. This suggests that the identified species represent new distribution records for the Philippines.

Taxonomic accounts

Class Insecta Linnaeus, 1758

Order Diptera Linnaeus, 1758

Family Chironomidae Newman, 1834

Subfamily Chironominae Goetghebuer, 1914

Genus *Kiefferulus* Goetghebuer, 1922

***Kiefferulus dilimanensis* sp. nov. Endico and Uy-Yabut, 2025 (Fig. 2A)**

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:AF4509CE-BE0E-4B06-8831-2B2D5B79F933

Etymology. The specific epithet *dilimanensis* is termed after the sampling site, UP Diliman.

Material examined. Holotype 1 male; Philippines: Luzon, Quezon City, Diliman, University of the Philippines, University Avenue Waterway (14°39'16"N 121°03'46"E), 19 March 2024; leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico. **Paratypes** 2 males; same as holotype. 1 male; Philippines: Luzon, Quezon City, Diliman, University of the Philippines, UP Lagoon (14°39'17"N 121°04'02"E), 23 May 2024; leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico.

Description. New male (n = 4), slide mounted, all with DNA sequences submitted to GenBank: **PX559725** (Holotype) & **PX559726, PX559727, PX559728** (Paratypes). Total body length 5790 (5630–5880); Wing width 660 (610–700); Wing length 2930 (2890–2970).

Head. Structures mostly yellowish brown in color, particularly of the vertex, antennae, and mouthparts. Vertex with setae (3–5 inner verticals, 5–6 outer verticals, and 6–7 post orbitals), and no frontal tubercles. Eyes hemispherical, dark brown, corona bare. Antenna plumose, with ring-like scape, large round pedicels, and 11 segments. Total length of 1st to 10th antennal segments: 234.24 (226.40–245.36), while 11th (last) segment: 1081.95 (1079.39–1084.14). Antennal ratio: 4.62 (4.61–4.77). Clypeus with 40 to 53 setae. Length of five maxillary palp segments: P1: 42.69 (37.85–49.93); P2: 36.39 (27.26–42.88); P3: 92.89 (91.99–93.94); P4: 123.28 (114.09–132.34); P5: 172.38 (170.90–172.61). Maxillary palp segment ratios, relative to the segment with the smallest length for the four specimens (in this case, 2nd segment): (specimen 1 - holotype) 1.16 : 1.00 : 2.19 : 3.09 : 3.99 ; (specimen 2 - paratype) 1.39 : 1.00 : 3.40 : 4.19 : 6.38 ; (specimen 3 - paratype) 1.06 : 1.00 : 2.37 : 3.11 : 4.43 ; (4) 1.15 : 1.00 : 2.54 : 3.45 : 4.71.

Thorax. Scutum medially and laterally brown-banded, while postnotum is almost entirely pigmented with brown. Thoracic setae: Acrostichals 22–33; Dorsocentrals 10–12; Prealars 5–6; Supraalars 3–5; Scutellars 11–13; Antepronotum bare.

Wing. Light yellow with pale brown veins. Brachiolium has two setae and two campaniform sensilla. Radius-Median (RM) vein almost brown in color. Costa (C) vein ends before M_{1+2} vein. Median (M) vein has 12 setae. Subcosta (Sc), R_1 , R_{2+3} , R_{4+5} , M_{1+2} , M_{3+4} , Cubital (Cu_1), and Fork of Cubital (FCu) veins are all bare. Squama has 11–15 setae, with 1 large brown triangular campaniform sensilla. Anal lobe flat, anal vein (An) ends proximal to FCu. Alula well-developed, rounded, and bare. Venarum ratio (VR) 0.05 (all). Radius ratio (RR) 0.35 (all), which shows R_{2+3} ends closer to the tip of R_1 than to the tip of R_{4+5} . R/Cu 1.48 (1.44–1.50) which shows the tip of R_{4+5} is distal to the tip of Cu_1 .

Legs. Yellowish in color. See Table 1 for complete leg segment lengths and ratios. Fore tibia ratio (fTR) 0.28 (0.25–0.29), typical of subfamily Chironominae genera. Fore tibiae without terminal spurs, while middle and hind tibiae with fused spurs in the terminal scales. Scales length 63.99 (62.14–65.54) and width 61.38 (59.19–63.12). Fused spurs of mid and hind tibia prominently sclerotized, almost equal in length.

Abdomen. Yellowish brown in color, 9-segmented, with the 9th segment or Tergite IX bearing the hypopygium. Tergites with numerous long lateral and median setae, about 100 μ m long each.

Figure 2. Adult male *Kiefferulus dilimanensis* sp. nov. Endico and Uy-Yabut, 2025: **A.** Habitus, and **B.** Hypopygium (closer look at **C.** Anal point, **D.** Inferior volsella, and **E.** Superior volsella).

Hypopygium (Fig. 2B). Anal tergite band strongly fused, Y-type, and without setae. Anal point (**Fig. 2C**) is strongly sclerotized, elongated and tapering towards base, apex is rounded, and no setae. Anal point length 133.55 (113.30–150.17), apex is about 140 far from the apex of inferior volsella (**Fig. 2D**). Inferior volsella spoon-like shaped, elongated, tapering towards base about 288.34 (263.80–299.89) long, apex body is almost sickle-shaped about 93.24 (90.18–98.82) wide, with megasetae prominent at the apex. Superior volsella (**Fig. 2E**) gently curved and hook-like, tapering towards the base, distal end narrows and slightly hooked downward resembling a curved claw, ridge at the base has internal 3–4 setae. Median volsella absent. Gonocoxite broad and elongate, flanks the central hypandrium and anal point, inner edges curve inward, with numerous long and dense megasetae. Gonocoxite length 231.79 (230.15–232.83), width 108.62 (102.98–118.34). Gonostylus medially broad, tapering towards apex 239.42 (208.81–257.75), width 73.15 (72.11–73.55).

Remarks. *Kiefferulus dilimanensis* sp. nov. is morphologically close to *K. tainanus* Kieffer, 1912. *K. tainanus* was collected from Tainan, Taiwan and originally described as *Tendipes tainanus* by Kieffer (1912). The only accessible reference that provides the original description of *T. tainanus* is Kieffer (1916), which briefly states that “the male anterior metatarsus one-fifth longer than the tibia, inferior appendages of the forceps strongly and abruptly enlarged at the extremity and this enlarged part is transverse and only slightly prolonged toward the terminal segment of the forceps.” This very general description can in fact apply to *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov.

Table 1. Leg segment lengths and ratios of *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov.

<i>K. dilimanensis</i> individuals	Legs	Fe	Ti	Ta ₁	Ta ₂	Ta ₃	Ta ₄	Ta ₅	fLR, mLR, hLR	fTR

1	P1	1083.11	996.37	1160.11	705.88	635.23	520.33	249.62	1.16	0.25
	P2	1025.1	1003.99	541.31	328.94	262.91	171.16	151.59	0.54	
	P3	1152.72	1264.36	765.73	470.41	429.36	230.22	161.36	0.61	
2	P1	981.77	868.06	1148.79	704.96	630.93	519.23	248.62	1.32	0.29
	P2	957.77	915.85	499.12	341.25	283.39	167.37	136.18	0.54	
	P3	1081.45	1158.24	755.93	450.36	419.34	220.72	149.46	0.65	
3	P1	1010.2	910.11	1150.4	705.24	636.11	520.67	248.61	1.26	0.27
	P2	1005.55	987.1	525.09	333.41	270.81	169.12	145.06	0.53	
	P3	1090.1	1187.25	760.88	470.41	430.31	225.11	149.22	0.64	
4	P1	991.77	860.06	1138.39	706.16	631.93	529.13	249.62	1.32	0.29
	P2	967.27	905.85	490.22	331.25	282.39	168.37	149.18	0.54	
	P3	1082.25	1166.41	745.43	451.26	429.33	221.52	151.36	0.64	
Average	P1	1016.71	908.65	1149.42	705.56	633.55	522.34	249.12	1.27	0.28
	P2	988.92	953.20	513.94	333.71	274.88	169.01	145.50	0.54	
	P3	1101.63	1194.07	756.99	460.61	427.09	224.39	152.85	0.63	

The taxonomic history of *K. tainanus* reflects the broader complexity of the genus *Kiefferulus*. The species has been transferred across several genera: to *Phytochironomus* (Kieffer, 1921), *Glyptotendipes* (Goetghebuer, 1937–1954), and later to *Chironomus* by Sasa (1979), who redescribed it based on Japanese material, noting 12-segmented antennae, AR of 3.68–3.76, a 4-segmented maxillary palp, and a prominent bare anal point. Hashimoto *et al.* (1981) also placed it in *Chironomus* but noted affinities with *Kiefferulus* and *Glyptotendipes*. It was subsequently transferred to *Kiefferulus* by Chaudhuri and Ghosh (1987) (as a probable synonym of *K. barbatitarsis*), then temporarily to *Nilodorum* Kieffer, 1921 by Cranston and Martin (1989), before being restored to *Kiefferulus* in a revision based on syntypes (Cranston *et al.*, 1990). More broadly, Cranston *et al.* (1990) synonymized the genera *Nilodorum* and *Carteronica* Strand, 1928 with *Kiefferulus*.

Morphologically, *K. tainanus* as described by Martin (2012) possesses a 5-segmented maxillary palp with a relatively longer ratio (4 : 3 : 5 : 8 : 10) compared to that of *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. (around 1 : 1 : 3 : 3 : 5). The latter also differs in having 11-segmented antennae and a higher AR (4.61–4.77) than reported by Sasa (1979). Furthermore, *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. has a large, heavily sclerotized anal point, which is absent in the descriptions of *K. tainanus*. Its hypopygium morphology also resembles that of the Indian species *K. atroxitarsis* Das and Mazumdar, 2012, although the latter bears setae on the swollen apex of the anal point. *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. is likewise similar to *K. barbatitarsis* (Kieffer, 1911), which Martin (2012) confirmed as distinct from *K. tainanus*. However, *K. barbatitarsis* has a more distally swollen superior volsella, while in *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. it is less swollen, and the anal point is prominent, bare, and strongly sclerotized.

***Kiefferulus calligaster* (Kieffer, 1911) new record (Fig. 3A)**

Chironomus calligaster (Kieffer, 1911): Cranston, 2007: 239

Material examined. 2 males; Philippines: Luzon, Quezon City, Diliman, University of the Philippines, UP Lagoon (14°39'17"N 121°04'02"E), 18 March 2024; leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico.

Description. Male (n = 2), 2 slide mounted; only 1 specimen was processed for sequencing, with the resulting DNA sequence submitted to GenBank: **PX559730**. Total length 5370 (both individuals); Wing width 650 (640 – 650); Wing length 2773 (2770 – 2780).

Head. Structures mostly yellowish brown in color, particularly of the vertex, antennae, and mouthparts, with some touches of red. Vertex with setae (3–4 inner verticals, 4–5 outer verticals, and 5–6 post orbitals), lacking frontal tubercles. Eyes hemispherical, dark brown, corona bare. Antenna plumose, with ring-like scape, large round pedicels, and 11 segments. Total length of 1st to 10th antennal segments: 219.47 (218.54–220.40), while 11th (last) segment: 1088.15 (1087.94–1088.36). Antennal ratio: 4.96 (4.94–4.98). Clypeus with 48 to 51 setae. Length of five maxillary palp segments: P1: 46.81 (45.71–47.91); P2: 44.18 (43.18–45.18); P3: 90.64 (90.14–91.14); P4: 132.76 (130.41–135.11); P5: 166.13 (165.15–167.11). Maxillary palp segment ratios, relative to the segment with the smallest length for the two specimens (in this case, 2nd segment): (specimen 1) 1.06 : 1.00 : 2.11 : 3.13 : 3.82 ; (specimen 2) 1.06 : 1.00 : 1.99 : 2.89 : 3.70.

Thorax. Scutum medially and laterally brown-banded, while postnotum is almost entirely pigmented with brown. Thoracic setae: Acrostichals 18–21; Dorsocentrals 11–12; Prealars 5; Supraalars 3; Scutellars 13; Antepnotum bare.

Figure 3. Adult male *Kiefferulus calligaster* (Kieffer, 1911): **A.** Habitus, and **B.** Hypopygium (closer look at **C.** Anal point, **D.** Inferior volsella, and **E.** Superior volsella).

Wing. Almost the same wing characteristics with *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. Light yellow with pale brown veins. Brachiolum has two setae and two campaniform sensilla. Radius-Median (RM) vein almost brown in color. Costa (C) vein ends before M_{1+2} vein. Median (M) vein has 12 setae. Subcosta (Sc), R_1 , R_{2+3} , R_{4+5} , M_{1+2} , M_{3+4} , Cubital (Cu_1), and Fork of Cubital (FCu) veins are all bare. Squama has 11–12 setae, with one large brown triangular campaniform sensilla. Anal lobe flat, anal vein (An) ends proximal to FCu. Alula well-developed, rounded, and bare. Venarum ratio (VR) 0.05 (both). Radius ratio (RR) 0.35 (0.34–0.35), which shows R_{2+3} ends closer to the tip of R_1 than to the tip of R_{4+5} . R/Cu 1.44 (1.44–1.45) which shows the tip of R_{4+5} is distal to the tip of Cu_1 .

Legs. Almost the same characteristics with *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. Yellowish in color. See **Table 2** for complete leg segment lengths and ratios. Fore tarsa-tibia ratio (fTR) 0.27 (0.27–0.28), typical of subfamily Chironominae genera. Fore tibiae without terminal spurs, while middle and hind tibiae with fused spurs in the terminal scales. Scales length 62.39 (61.24–63.54) and width 59.21 (59.19–59.22). Fused spurs of mid and hind tibia prominently sclerated, almost equal in length.

Abdomen. Yellowish brown in color, 9-segmented, with the 9th segment or Tergite IX bearing the hypopygium. Tergite VI– XI slightly narrower and browner. Tergites with numerous long lateral and median setae, about 100 μ m long each.

Hypopygium (Fig. 3B). Anal tergite band strongly fused, Y-type, and without setae. Anal point (**Fig. 3C**) is slightly sclerated, elongated and narrow, apex is rounded, and no setae. Anal point length 91.57 (91.12–92.02), apex is about 130 far from the apex of inferior volsella (**Fig. 3D**). Inferior volsella spoon-like shaped, elongated, tapering towards base about 301.32 (300.32–302.32) long, apex body is almost sickle-shaped about 86.19 (85.55–86.82) wide, with megasetae prominent at the apex. Superior volsella (**Fig. 3E**) prominently curved (about 133° angle) and hook-like, tapering towards the apex, directed towards the anal point, more rounded tip compared to *Kiefferulus* sp., ridge at the base has internal 5 setae. Median volsella absent. Gonocoxite broad and elongate, flanks the central hypandrium and anal point, inner edges curve inward, with numerous long and dense megasetae. Gonocoxite length 244.69 (244.18–245.20), width 108.17 (109.27–110.37). Gonostylus broad from base up to more than the median area, tapering towards apex, length 231.25 (229.25–233.25), width 84.90 (83.89–85.91).

Remarks. The hypopygium and inferior volsella morphology match the original and redescribed illustrations of *K. calligaster*. This species differs from *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. mainly on shapes of anal point and superior volsella. Superior volsella of *K. calligaster* is prominently curved (about 133° angle) and hook-like, while that of *K. dilimanensis* is also hook-like but gently curved and claw-shaped. Anal point of *K. calligaster* is much narrower compared to that of *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. Both without frontal tubercles and with costa vein ending before the M_{1+2} veins. In contrast, *Chironomus* species do not possess frontal tubercles and have costa veins ending at R_{4+5} vein.

Table 2. Leg segment lengths and ratios of *K. calligaster*.

<i>K. calligaster</i> individuals	Legs	Fe	Ti	Ta ₁	Ta ₂	Ta ₃	Ta ₄	Ta ₅	fLR, mLR, hLR	fTR
1	P1	1002.8	895.3	1127.6	693.5	612.2	508.4	239.6	1.26	0.27
	P2	980.6	960.4	538.8	322.7	261.3	170.7	144.9	0.56	
	P3	1071.2	1201.5	754.3	482.2	438.1	233.9	150.8	0.63	
2	P1	991.71	855.06	1129.35	706.15	612.33	519.22	240.12	1.32	0.28

	P2	967.27	955.15	490.22	331.25	282.39	168.37	149.18	0.51	
	P3	1082.25	1166.41	745.43	451.26	429.33	221.52	151.36	0.64	
Average	P1	997.26	875.18	1128.48	699.83	612.27	513.81	239.86	1.29	0.27
	P2	973.94	957.78	514.51	326.98	271.85	169.54	147.04	0.54	
	P3	1076.73	1183.96	749.87	466.73	433.72	227.71	151.08	0.63	

Genus *Chironomus* Meigen, 1803

***Chironomus circumdatus* (Kieffer, 1916) new record (Fig. 4A)**

Chironomus basitibialis Tokunaga, 1936: Martin, 2020: 22

Chironomus bharati Singh & Kulshretha, 1976: Martin, 2020: 22

Chironomus costatus sensu Karunakaran, 1969: Martin, 2020: 22

Chironomus plumatisetigerus Tokunaga, 1964: Martin & Saxena, 2009: 14

Chironomus setonis Tokunaga, 1936: Martin, 2020: 22

Material examined. 1 male; Philippines: Luzon, Quezon City, Diliman, University of the Philippines, UP Lagoon (14°39'17"N 121°04'02"E), 18 March, 2024; leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico.

Description. Male (n = 1), slide mounted, with DNA sequence submitted to GenBank: **PX559732**. Total length 6040; Wing width 730; Wing length 3090.

Figure 4. Adult male *Chironomus circumdatus* (Kieffer, 1916): **A.** Habitus, and **B.** Hypopygium (closer look at **C.** Anal point, **D.** Inferior volsella, and **E.** Superior volsella).

Head. Structures mostly yellowish brown in color, particularly of the vertex, antennae, and mouthparts. Vertex with prominent cylindrical frontal tubercles with length 27.00 and width 16.00. Eyes hemispherical, dark brown, corona bare. Antenna plumose, with ring-like scape, large round pedicels, and 11 segments. Total length of 1st to 10th antennal segments: 850.83, while 11th segment: 1155.03. Antennal ratio 1.36. Clypeus with about 30 setae. Length of five maxillary palp segments: P1: 50.5; P2: 50.46; P3: 227.07; P4: 222.01; P5: 365.50. Maxillary palp segment ratios, relative to the segment with the smallest length (in this case, 2nd segment): 1.00 : 1.00 : 4.50 : 4.40 : 7.24.

Thorax. Yellow; scutum with three orange-yellow stripes with darker lateral margins; anterior margin behind head fuscous; postscutellum pale brown caudally. Thoracic setae: Acrostichals 15; Dorsocentrals 21; Prealars 5; Supraalars 3; Scutellars 25; Anteprenotum bare.

Table 3. Leg segment lengths and ratios of *C. circumdatus*.

<i>C. circumdatus</i> individual	Legs	Fe	Ti	Ta ₁	Ta ₂	Ta ₃	Ta ₄	Ta ₅	fLR, mLR, hLR	fTR
1	P1	1140.20	1061.22	1610.12	830.22	743.21	644.45	324.15	1.52	0.52
	P2	1262.15	1125.1	706.06	422.74	287.31	155.33	137.12	0.63	
	P3	1399.57	1380.42	1058.99	533.66	429.83	233.4	155.74	0.77	

Wing. Light yellow with pale brown veins. Brachiolium has approximately two setae and two campaniform sensilla. Radius-Median (RM) vein slightly brown in color. Costa (C) vein ends at R₄₊₅ vein. Median (M) vein has eight to nine setae. Subcosta (Sc) R₂₊₃, M₁₊₂, M₃₊₄, Cubital (Cu₁), and Fork of Cubital (FCu) veins are all bare. Squama has nine setae, with one large brown triangular campaniform sensilla. Anal lobe slightly rounded, anal vein (An) ends proximal to FCu. Alula prominent, slightly round to flat. Anal lobe is about 210.00 which is longer than the alula. Creates depression slightly deep between Alula and Anal lobe. Venarum ratio (VR) 1.09. Radius ratio (RR) 0.29 which shows R₂₊₃ ends closer to the tip of R1 than to the tip of R₄₊₅. R/Cu 1.40 which shows the tip of R₄₊₅ is distal to the tip of Cu₁.

Legs. Almost Yellowish in color. See **Table 3** for complete leg segment lengths and ratios. Fore tarsa-tibia ratio (fTR) 0.52, typical of subfamily Chironominae genera. Fore tibiae without terminal spurs, while middle and hind tibiae with fused spurs in the terminal scales. Scales length 53.29 and width 13.32. Fused spurs of mid and hind tibia prominently sclerotized, almost equal in length.

Abdomen. Yellowish; Tergite I is entirely pale, tergites II–VII each bear a central oval dark patch bordered by pale regions; the basal half of tergite V and almost the entire surfaces of tergites VIII–IX are pale brown. This quite differs from the descriptions provided by Sasa (1978) and Martin (2020) that *C. circumdatus* has only dark patches on tergites II–IV and tergites V–VIII are dark.

Hypopygium (Fig. 4B). Anal tergite band strongly fused, S-type. Anal point (**Fig. 4C**) not sclerotized, narrow from the base then rounded at the apex, no setae. Anal point length 98.82, narrow from the base and increasing width halfway, round apex (**Fig. 4D**). Inferior volsella cylindrical with a width that starts to narrow down about in the middle, about 255.01 long, apex body is round, about 51.77 wide, with megasetae prominent at the apex. Superior volsella (**Fig. 4E**) elongated, gently curved and hook-like, with distal process horn-shaped, S-type according to Sasa (1978), directed towards the inferior volsella. Median volsella absent. Gonocoxite broad and elongate tapering towards apex, flanks the central hypandrium and anal point, inner edges curve inward, with numerous long and dense megasetae. Gonocoxite length 230.28, width 77.35. Gonostylus broad from base, slightly or gently reducing about halfway or tapering towards apex, length 207.63, width 77.35.

Remarks. The UP Diliman specimen exhibits diagnostic features consistent with those in the original descriptions.

***Chironomus crassiforceps* Kieffer, 1916 new record (Fig. 5A)**

Chironomus esakai Tokunaga, 1940: Martin, 2020: 31

Chironomus insolens Johannsen, 1946 - synonymised with *C. esakai* by Hardy (1960): Martin, 2020: 31

Yaesecundus iriobeceus Sasa and Susuki, 2000: Martin, 2020: 31

Chironomus daitoabeus Sasa and Susuki, 2001: Martin, 2020: 31

Daitoyusurika daitofegea Sasa and Susuki, 2001: Martin, 2020: 31

Material examined. 3 male; Philippines: Luzon, Quezon City, Diliman, University of the Philippines, UP Lagoon (14°39'17"N 121°04'02"E), 18 March 2024; leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico.

Description. Male (n = 3), slide mounted, only 1 specimen was processed for sequencing, with the resulting DNA sequence submitted to GenBank: **PX559731**. Total length 5230 (5160–5270); Wing width 650 (630–680); Wing length 3070 (3000–3210).

Head. Structures mostly yellowish brown in color, particularly of the vertex, antennae, and mouthparts. Vertex with prominent cylindrical frontal tubercles with length 39.90 (39.61–21.55) and width 12.84 (12.57–13.11). Eyes hemispherical, dark brown, corona bare. Antenna plumose, with ring-like scape, large round pedicels, and 12 segments. Total length of 1st to 10th antennal segments: 392.40 (377.99–400.11), while 11th segment: 726.96 (680.11–780.11) and 12th segment (short last segment): 83.07 (50.11 – 129.00). Antennal ratio (combined length of segment 11 and 12 over the combined length of segments 1–10.: 2.06 (1.88–2.25). Clypeus with about 50 setae. Length of five maxillary palp segments: P1: 48.20 (45.25–50.22); P2: 55.01 (53.03–57.02); P3: 172.22 (146.71–188.22); P4: 179.53 (151.81–195.11); P5: 253.71 (228.58–267.12). Maxillary palp segment ratios, relative to the segment with the smallest length for the four specimens (in this case, 1st segment): (specimen 1) 1.00 : 1.17 : 3.24 : 3.36 : 5.05 ; (specimen 2) 1.00 : 1.12 : 3.70 : 3.90 : 5.40 ; (specimen 3) 1.00 : 1.14 : 3.75 : 3.88 : 5.32.

Thorax. Thorax yellow; scutum white with four pale brown vittae; anterior margin behind head fuscous; postscutellum pale brown caudally; pleural and sternal sclerites pale brownish yellow, all consistent with the description of Tokunaga 1940. Thoracic setae: Acrostichals 15; Dorsocentrals 19–20; Prealaris 5; Supraalaris 1–3; Scutellaris 20–21; Anteppronotum bare.

Wing. Light yellow with pale brown veins, crossvein black. Brachiolum has approximately two setae and two campaniform sensilla. Radius-Median (RM) vein almost dark brown in color. Costa (C) vein ends at R₄₊₅ vein. Median (M) vein has 8–9 setae. Subcosta (Sc) R₂₊₃, M₁₊₂, M₃₊₄, Cubital (Cu₁), and Fork of Cubital (FCu) veins are all bare. Squama has 9–10 setae, with one large brown triangular campaniform sensilla. Anal lobe slightly rounded, anal vein (An) ends proximal to FCu. Alula prominent, slightly round to flat. Anal lobe is about 214.99 which is longer than the alula. Creates depression slightly deep between Alula and Anal lobe. Venarum ratios (VR) 1.09 (for all three specimens). Radius ratio (RR) 0.41 (for all three specimens) which shows R₂₊₃ ends closer to the tip of R₁ than to the tip of R₄₊₅. R/Cu 1.41 (1.39–1.44) which shows the tip of R₄₊₅ is distal to the tip of Cu₁.

Legs. Yellowish in color. See **Table 4** for complete leg segment lengths and ratios. Fore tarsi-tibia ratio (fTR) 0.31 (0.29–0.32), typical of subfamily Chironominae genera. Fore tibiae without terminal spurs, while middle and hind tibiae with fused spurs in the terminal scales. Scales length 60.04 (59.21–

60.59) and width 51.78 (50.94–52.49). Fused spurs of mid and hind tibia prominently sclerotized, almost equal in length.

Figure 5. Adult male *Chironomus crassiforceps* Kieffer, 1916: **A.** Habitus, and **B.** Hypopygium (closer look at **C.** Anal point, **D.** Inferior volsella, and **E.** Superior volsella).

Abdomen. Tergites I–V are plain pale yellow, no bands or spots. Caudal tergites VI to IX are brownish.

Hypopygium (Fig. 5B). Anal tergite band strongly fused. Anal point (**Fig. 5C**) 52 (92.42–93.01), has a dorsal sclerotized pointed ridge with ventral extension in the apex that appears like a rounded fin in the dorsal view. Widest center width of the apex about 65.48 (65.00–66.10). Inferior volsella (**Fig. 5D**) wide and elongated, about 345.07 (341.12–350.98) in length and 53.62 (53.29–54.11) in width, apex body is round, about 23.24 (22.11–24.44) wide, with megasetae prominent at the apex. Superior volsella (**Fig. 5E**) narrow or slender, slightly curved, long and cylindrical about 98.78 (98.12–99.12) long, apex body is round, about 15.35 (14.99–16.85) wide. Median volsella absent. Gonocoxite broad but short, tapering towards apex, with numerous long and dense megasetae. Gonocoxite length 185.07 (175.99–190.11), width 142.76 (140.33–145.52). Gonostylus broad and elongated, slightly swollen at mid-length, where it also slightly narrows in width. Gonostylus length 277.55 (275.44–279.11), width 128.28 (127.01–129.81).

Remarks. The UP Diliman specimens exhibit diagnostic features consistent with those in the original descriptions.

Table 4. Leg segment lengths and ratios of *C. crassiforceps*.

<i>C. crassiforceps</i>	Legs	Fe	Ti	Ta ₁	Ta ₂	Ta ₃	Ta ₄	Ta ₅	fLR, mLR, hLR	fTR

individuals										
1	P1	1261.8 5	1199.1 2	1743.1 1	875.2 2	784.2 1	762.1 1	350.2 1	1.45	0.29
	P2	1411.0 6	1432.3 2	621.8	358.0 8	270.3 1	219.2 6	148.7 4	0.43	
	P3	1611.8 8	1598.1 2	785.64	468.7 6	440.5 4	200.9 3	201.9 5	0.49	
2	P1	1374.1 2	1182.5 2	1757.2 8	897.9 6	789.8 9	763.6 9	375.9 7	1.49	0.32
	P2	1454.9 9	1448.2 3	658.23	338.6 2	312.7 4	202.3 8	190.1 9	0.45	
	P3	1618.6 9	1561.4 4	822	491.9	426.6 5	229.9 4	192.2 5	0.53	
3	P1	1358.5 1	1085.7 6	1749.3	860.8	774.9 3	741.3 4	344.0 2	1.61	0.32
	P2	1362.5 1	1301.3 7	594.74	365.2 2	308.4 6	211.2 7	196.2 9	0.46	
	P3	1511.3 4	1384.6 7	829.4	511.6 2	432.4 1	257.7 4	174.2 6	0.60	
Average	P1	1331.4 9	1155.8 0	1749.9 0	877.9 9	783.0 1	755.7 1	356.7 3	1.52	0.31
	P2	1409.5 2	1393.9 7	624.92	353.9 7	297.1 7	210.9 7	178.4 1	0.45	
	P3	1580.6 4	1514.7 4	812.35	490.7 6	433.2 0	229.5 4	189.4 9	0.54	

***Chironomus flaviplumus* Tokunaga, 1940 new record (Fig. 6A)**

Einfeldia okisiroia Sasa, 1993; Martin (2020): 36

Chironomus samoensis Edwards; Hashimoto, 1977 (fide Martin, 2020); status doubtful (Sasa, 1978, fide Martin, 2020)

Material examined. 1 male; Philippines: Luzon, Quezon City, Diliman, University of the Philippines, UP Lagoon (14°39'17"N 121°04'02"E), 18 March 2024; leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico. 3 males; University Avenue Waterways (14°39'16"N 121°03'46"E), 19 March 2024, leg. C. J. C. Uy-Yabut and H. A. C. Endico.

Description. Male (n = 4), only one specimen was processed for sequencing, with the resulting DNA sequence submitted to GenBank: **PX559729**. Total length 5840 (5580–6000); Wing width 580 (540–680); Wing length 3000 (2980–3010).

Head. Structures mostly yellowish brown in color, particularly of the vertex, antennae, and mouthparts. Vertex with setae (3–5 inner verticals, 4–5 outer verticals, and 5–6 post orbitals), with short frontal tubercles with length 20.83 (20.10–21.55) and width 12.89 (11.01–15.12). Eyes hemispherical, dark brown, corona bare. Antenna plumose, with ring-like scape, large round pedicels, and 11 segments. Total length of 1st to 10th antennal segments: 292.50 (290.22–298.66), while 11th (last segment): 1074.27 (912.76 – 1210.11). Antennal ratio: 3.68 (3.14–4.17). Clypeus with 48 to 50 setae. Length of four maxillary palp segments: P1: 93.35 (90.11–98.64); P2: 171.09 (155.99–187.59); P3: 191.45 (180.11–217.93); P4: 299.70 (279.36–358.76). Maxillary palp segment ratios, relative to the segment with the smallest length for the four specimens (in this case, 1st segment): (specimen 1) 1.00 : 1.82 : 1.91 : 2.98 ; (specimen 2) 1.00 : 1.90 : 2.21 : 3.64 ; (specimen 3) 1.00 : 1.88 : 1.97 : 3.10 ; (specimen 4) 1.00 : 1.72 : 2.10 : 3.10.

Thorax. Scutum medially and laterally orange to yellow-banded. Thoracic setae: Acrostichals 15–16; Dorsocentrals 17–20; Prealars 5–6; Supraalars 3; Scutellars 20–24; Antepnotum bare.

Wing. Light yellow with pale brown veins. Brachiolum has two setae and two campaniform sensilla. Radius-Median (RM) vein almost brown in color. Costa (C) vein ends at R₄₊₅ vein. Median (M) vein has 7–9 setae. Subcosta (Sc) R₂₊₃, M₁₊₂, M₃₊₄, Cubital (Cu₁), and Fork of Cubital (FCu) veins are all bare. Squama has 14–15 setae, with 1 large brown triangular campaniform sensilla. Anal lobe slight rounded, anal vein (An) ends proximal to FCu. Alula prominent, slightly round to flat. Anal lobe is 230.11 which is longer than the alula. Creates depression deep between Alula and Anal lobe. Venarum ratios (VR) 1.01 (0.99–1.02). Radius ratio (RR) 0.25 all four. which shows R₂₊₃ ends closer to the tip of R1 than to the tip of R₄₊₅. R/Cu 1.44 (1.44–1.45) which shows the tip of R₄₊₅ is distal to the tip of Cu₁.

Legs. Yellowish in color. See **Table 5** for complete leg segment lengths and ratios. Fore tibia ratio (fTR) 0.36 (0.31–0.39), typical of subfamily Chironominae genera. Fore tibiae without terminal spurs, while middle and hind tibiae with fused spurs in the terminal scales. Scales length 65.90 (64.11 – 66.96) and width 52.96 (51.98 – 54.42). Fused spurs of mid and hind tibia prominently sclerated, almost equal in length.

Abdomen. Yellow or greenish yellow abdominal tergites. Tergite I is pale. Tergites II, III, and IV have large oval dark spots at the center. Tergites V and VI also have spots but faint and small compared to those of tergites II, III, and IV. Between tergites VI and VII is a brown band below the faint spot in tergite VI extending towards the center of tergite VII, shaped like oval but with pointed end at tergite VII.

Hypopygium (Fig. 6B). Anal tergite band strongly fused, S-type, and without setae. Anal point (**Fig. 6C**), is not sclerated, narrow from the base then rounded at the apex, no setae. Anal point length 80.22 (79.72–81.12) (**Fig. 6D**). Inferior volsella cylindrical with a width that starts to narrow down about in the middle, about 102.49 (83.98–156.93) long, apex body is round, about 25.16 (21.98–34.20) wide, with megasetae prominent at the apex. Superior volsella (**Fig. 6E**) strongly beaked, not gently curved, directed towards the inferior volsella. Median volsella absent. Gonocoxite broad and elongate tapering towards apex, flanks the central hypandrium and anal point, inner edges curve inward, with numerous long and dense megasetae. Gonocoxite length 173.45 (157.57–205.90), width 62.32 (55.77–75.35). Gonostylus broad from base, slightly or gently reducing about halfway or tapering towards apex, length 167.74 (153.06–203.66), width 32.53 (31.99–33.21).

Remarks. Species found in UP Diliman has some characters of the *C. flaviplumus* Type A (described by Sasa in 1978 and classified as Type A by Martin in 2020), having the following similarly or within the ratios by Sasa (1978): 1.) strongly beaked superior volsella and not gently curved, 2.) oval spots from tergite II–IV 3.) 4-segmented palpus, 4.) frontal tubercles length 20.83 (20.10–21.55) and width 12.89 (11.01–15.12), 5.) AR 3.68 (3.14–4.17) 6.) fLR 1.92 (1.83–2.02), 7.) fTR 0.36 (0.31–0.39).

However, it also differs in Type A by having only 11 segments of antenna (12 in Sasa, 1978) and having a gonostylus only slightly or gently reducing about halfway (reduces sharply in Sasa, 1978).

Figure 6. Adult male *Chironomus flaviplumus* Tokunaga, 1940: **A.** Habitus, and **B.** Hypopygium (closer look at **C.** Anal point, **D.** Inferior volsella, and **E.** Superior volsella).

The gonostylus resembles that of *C. flaviplumus* Type B. However, molecular analysis in reference to the maximum likelihood tree (**Fig. 7**), the Philippine specimen clusters with other *C. flaviplumus* Type C, which seems to be closer to *C. claggi* Tokunaga, 1965 than the other *flaviplumus* types. There is currently no description about this type according to Martin (2020) since the DNA barcode sequence is the only available reference with limited information about the larva. Given this molecular analysis, the Philippine species will be temporarily identified as *C. flaviplumus* Type C until further studies about this type are provided. This type is closer to *C. claggi* which makes sense since it superficially resembles *C. flaviplumus*. However, the Philippine species is morphologically not the same to *C. claggi* Tokunaga, 1965 which has the following: 1.) 5-segmented palpus, 2.) slender superior volsella, 3.) AR 2.7 (2.50 – 2.85), and 4.) fLR 1.7 (1.66-1.77). BLAST search in NCBI also shows it can be related to *C. samoensis* Edwards, 1928 which has the following: 1.) 5-segmented palpus, 2.) superior volsella also peaked but not the same angle with *flaviplumus* nor *claggi*, 3.) AR 2.86 (2.7–3.09) and 4.) fLR 1.81 (1.75–1.84), which all may not be applicable to the Philippine species. The number of antennae segments is not mentioned both from the descriptions of *C. claggi* and *C. samoensis*, and even in *C. flaviplumus* Type B.

The Philippine species, discriminated mainly by having 11-segmented antenna and 4-segmented palps, is tentatively identified as *C. flaviplumus* Type C, with the recognition that it likely belongs to a broader *C. samoensis-claggi-flaviplumus* species complex as seen in the molecular analysis, pending further integrative taxonomic work.

Table 5. Leg segment lengths and ratios of *C. flaviplumus*.

C. flaviplumus individuals	Legs	Fe	Ta₁	Ta₂	Ta₃	Ta₄	Ta₅	Ta₁	fLR, mLR, hLR	fTR
1	P1	1090.11	870.09	1710.11	950.43	815.6	700.15	320.94	1.97	0.37
	P2	1160.99	1050.99	630.1	390.41	260.42	139.12	139.41	0.60	
	P3	1240.55	1235.13	1030.11	560.1	415.21	249.12	169.44	0.83	
2	P1	1096.8	866.97	1750.91	970.04	850.34	740.12	340.43	2.02	0.39
	P2	1154.34	1022.79	629.32	387.04	276.86	152.58	136.25	0.62	
	P3	1232.69	1241.76	1031.81	572.04	403.01	250.25	167.8	0.83	
3	P1	1046.06	931.86	1720.55	980.96	843.76	690.71	350.83	1.85	0.38
	P2	1131.75	1009.52	655.1	356.61	241.36	136.25	81.57	0.65	
	P3	1350.63	1336.74	1020.36	559.94	416.43	223.34	141.27	0.76	
4	P1	1253.65	1036.2	1898.74	966.36	853.78	722.22	318.24	1.83	0.31
	P2	1320.4	1166.61	748.58	414.35	289.87	172.67	109.05	0.64	
	P3	1484.28	1423.96	1110.56	601.92	457.24	242.42	160.37	0.78	
Average	P1	1121.66	926.28	1770.08	966.95	840.87	713.30	332.61	1.92	0.36
	P2	1191.87	1062.48	665.78	387.10	267.13	150.16	116.57	0.63	
	P3	1327.04	1309.40	1048.21	573.50	422.97	241.28	159.72	0.80	

Key to the Adult Males of *Kiefferulus* and *Chironomus* from UP Diliman

The following dichotomous key is provided to facilitate the identification of adult males of *Kiefferulus* and *Chironomus* collected from the University of the Philippines Diliman campus. Diagnostic characters used in this key are based on external morphology of the head, wings, and hypopygium, particularly features of the frontal tubercles, antennae, anal point, and shape of the superior and inferior volsellae. These characters are consistent with diagnostic criteria commonly used in Chironomidae taxonomy. The key covers four species of *Chironomus* (*C. crassiforceps*, *C. flaviplumus*, *C. circumdatus*) and two species of *Kiefferulus* (*K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. and *K. calligaster*), which are newly described from the Philippines.

- 1a.** Frontal tubercles absent; costa vein ends before M₁₊₂ vein *Kiefferulus 2*
1b. Frontal tubercles present; costa vein ends at R₄₊₅ vein *Chironomus 3*
2a. Anal point strongly sclerotized, elongated, tapering toward base; superior volsella narrow, hook-like and slightly claw-shaped; inferior volsella elongate, spoon-like, apex sickle-shaped *K. dilimanensis*
2b. Anal point less sclerotized, narrower, rounded at apex; superior volsella prominently curved at ~133°

- tip rounded; inferior volsella elongate, spoon-like but narrower
 *K. calligaster*
- 3a.** Antenna with 12 flagellomeres; anal point with a dorsal sclerotized pointed ridge and ventral extension
 at apex forming a rounded fin in dorsal view
 *C. crassiforceps*
- 3b.** Antenna with 11 flagellomeres; anal point rounded **4**
- 4a.** Superior volsella strongly beaked, not gently curved, directed toward inferior volsella
 *C. flaviplumus*
- 4b.** Superior volsella elongated, gently curved and hook-like, with distal process horn-shaped
 *C. circumdatus*

Molecular Analysis

To strengthen the analysis, paper of Martin (2020) regarding the identification of oriental chironomids was referred to, where he provided BOLD Bin links for COI sequences of *Chironomus crassiforceps* (BOLD:AAJ4269), *C. circumdatus* (BOLD:AAG5483), and *C. flaviplumus* which was noted as occurring in three types: Type A (BOLD:ACQ8383), Type B (BOLD:AAW3997), and Type C (BOLD:AAV5954). BOLD Bins group sequences that algorithmically fall under a single species, and in some cases, specimens labeled as *C. magnivalvia* were placed within the *C. crassiforceps* bin. This accounts for the notation e.g. “(*C. magnivalvia*) *C. crassiforceps*” in the maximum likelihood tree. The same context applies to the format “(*Chironomus* sp.) *C. flaviplumus* Type B” and “(*C. incertipennis*) *C. flaviplumus* Type B” which are identified as *Chironomus* sp. and *C. incertipennis*, respectively, in BOLD but both fall under the *C. flaviplumus* Type B bin. Additional species such as *C. claggi* and *C. samoensis* were incorporated to test their distinctness from *C. flaviplumus*, while *K. barbatitarsis* was added to provide comparative context for *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. and *K. tainanus*. Sequences from GenBank were also crosschecked (see **Table 6**).

The maximum likelihood (ML) tree based on COI sequences (658 bp) (**Fig. 7**) provides strong support for the placement of the newly described *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. within the *Kiefferulus* clade (bootstrap = 99). Philippine sequences (Phi 1–5) clustered together with high support, forming a distinct branch separated from *K. tainanus* (Japan and China) and *K. barbatitarsis* (Thailand and China). The K2P genetic distance between the Philippine *K. dilimanensis* and sequences of *K. tainanus* and *K. barbatitarsis* ranged from 9.00–9.43%, a level far exceeding the usual intraspecific divergence reported for chironomids (<3%) and well within interspecific thresholds. This molecular distinctiveness is consistent with the diagnostic morphological traits of *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov., including its 11-segmented antenna (12 in *K. tainanus*), higher antennal ratio, and heavily sclerotized anal point, which distinguish it from both *K. tainanus* and *K. barbatitarsis*. Together, these data strongly support its recognition as a new species.

The Philippine *K. calligaster* clustered closely with conspecifics from India, Thailand, and Pakistan (bootstrap = 99). The K2P distances between Philippine and other *K. calligaster* sequences ranged from 1.49–2.83%, well within expected intraspecific variation. This confirms that the Philippine specimens represent the same species, with morphology (narrower anal point, prominently curved superior volsella) aligning with established descriptions. This represents the first confirmed record of *K. calligaster* in the Philippines.

The Philippine *C. crassiforceps* clustered with other Asian representatives (Bangladesh, India, Thailand) with strong support (bootstrap = 99). The K2P divergence between the Philippine and Asian populations was 3.02–4.34%, a level consistent with intraspecific geographic variation in *Chironomus*. In contrast, comparisons with more remote Pacific populations (United States Minor Outlying Islands, French Polynesia, and Tuvalu) revealed much higher divergence values (6.77–7.40%). This degree of genetic

distance approaches or even exceeds thresholds typically observed between congeneric species of *Chironomus*, raising the possibility that Pacific island populations may represent a distinct lineage or even an undescribed species.

At present, however, these populations are still treated under the name *C. crassiforceps* due to the absence of a formal taxonomic revision that integrates molecular and morphological data across its range. Morphologically, Philippine specimens conform to the diagnostic characters of *C. crassiforceps* (e.g., 12-segmented antenna, dorsal ridge on anal point, whitish scutum with pale vittae), but material from remote Pacific localities remains poorly described or unavailable for direct comparison. Until such integrative work is undertaken, *C. crassiforceps* is best regarded as a widely distributed taxon that may encompass multiple geographically structured lineages, with the Philippine population clearly belonging to the Asian cluster.

The Philippine *C. circumdatus* was firmly placed with Asian representatives (bootstrap = 99), with extremely low K2P divergence (0.00–1.12%). This indicates a high degree of genetic uniformity across its distribution from South to East Asia, consistent with its well-defined morphological features, such as frontal tubercles, S-type superior volsella, and abdominal tergite coloration.

The Philippine *C. flaviplumus* clustered with Type C sequences (bootstrap = 93), with K2P distances of only 0.55–1.12%, well within intraspecific levels. Morphologically, the Philippine material combines features overlapping Types A and B (beaked superior volsella, tergite spots, AR range), but differs in having an 11-segmented antenna and 4-segmented palpus. Its clustering with Type C supports the view that this taxon belongs to the broader *C. samoensis-claggi-flaviplumus* complex, where cryptic or semi-cryptic diversity is known. Pending a comprehensive integrative revision, the Philippine specimens are best regarded as *C. flaviplumus* Type C.

The use of COI barcodes in species delimitation requires careful interpretation, as the range of overlap between intra- and interspecific variation depends on the taxonomic group (Meier *et al.*, 2006). As noted by Kang *et al.* (2022a), in Chironomidae, average intraspecific divergences are usually low, ranging from 0.9–2.3% (Ekrem *et al.*, 2007; Sinclair and Gresens, 2008). However, cryptic diversity has been reported within a 2–5% range (Smith *et al.*, 2012; 2014), and higher thresholds of 4–8% have been suggested for *Tanytarsus* and *Polypedilum* (Lin *et al.*, 2015; Song *et al.*, 2016). Kang *et al.* (2022a) further documented intraspecific divergence exceeding 8% in three species (*Dicrotendipes nervosus*, *Microchironomus tener*, *Ablabesmyia longistyla*), where no significant morphological differences were found, highlighting cases of cryptic taxa or deep genetic structure. Such “deep intraspecific divergence” may arise from misidentifications, ancestral polymorphisms, or introgression (Park *et al.*, 2011). A large-scale barcode study of Korean Chironomidae also emphasized that the “barcode gap” remains useful in most groups, with a roughly 20-fold difference between maximum intraspecific and minimum interspecific K2P distances in well-sampled species (Kim *et al.*, 2013). Yet, exceptions highlight the need for integrative approaches combining molecular, morphological, and geographic evidence. Within *Rheotanytarsus* Thienemann and Bause, 1913, for example, intraspecific divergence thresholds of 5.77–7% were accepted due to high variability across populations (Yao *et al.*, 2025).

Similarly, Pramual *et al.* (2016) emphasized that while DNA barcoding generally performs well in Chironomidae (>90% identification success; Carew *et al.*, 2005; Ekrem *et al.*, 2007; Kim *et al.*, 2012), it also uncovers hidden diversity. In their study, four species (*Chironomus kiiensis* Tokunaga, 1936, *C. striatipennis* Kieffer, 1910, *Kiefferulus calligaster*, and *K. tainanus*) displayed high intraspecific divergence (>3% K2P), suggesting the presence of cryptic species. This corroborates earlier work showing that divergence values above 3% may indicate species complexes in Diptera, including Chironomidae and Simuliidae (Pfenninger *et al.*, 2007; Pramual *et al.*, 2011; Pramual and Adler, 2014; Rivera and Currie, 2009). However, it should be noted that one of the *K. tainanus* used by Pramual *et al.* (2016) barcoded as

COTW018-08 is recognized as *K. barbatitarsis* in the study of Martin (2020) where they recognized that *K. tainanus* and *K. barbatitarsis* are distinct from one another through morphological and molecular analysis through comparison of polymorphic sites in the bases of mitochondrial COI sequences. In the ML tree provided (Fig. 7), *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. forms a separate clade from *K. tainanus* and *K. barbatitarsis* which can confirm that the species found in the Philippines can be distinct from the two, with significant morphological differences. Therefore, in this case, a threshold of interspecific variation at >9% (K2P genetic distance of *K. dilimanensis* sp. nov. from *K. tainanus* and *K. barbatitarsis* ranged from 9.00–9.43%) can be applied to these *Kiefferulus* species. Indeed, this is one of the evidences that species delimitation or intra- and interspecific variation depends on the taxonomic group (Meier *et al.*, 2006).

Philippine *K. calligaster* showed K2P divergences of 1.49–2.83% relative to conspecifics from India, Thailand, and Pakistan. These values fall within the expected intraspecific range of chironomids (0.9–2.3%; Ekrem *et al.*, 2007; Kang *et al.*, 2022a). Interestingly, Pramual *et al.* (2016) noted that *K. calligaster* sometimes exhibits higher intraspecific divergence (>3%) in Thailand, raising the possibility of cryptic diversity within this taxon. However, the Philippine material falls below this threshold, supporting its current conspecific status.

In *C. crassiforceps*, Philippine populations diverged from Asian populations (Bangladesh, India, Thailand) by 3.02–4.34%, slightly above the typical intraspecific mean but still within ranges reported for widespread species and putative cryptic complexes (Pramual *et al.*, 2016). By contrast, divergences of 6.77–7.40% with Pacific populations (French Polynesia, Tuvalu, U.S. Minor Outlying Islands) approach levels that often separate species in Chironomidae. Although currently treated as *C. crassiforceps*, this suggests possible geographic structuring or cryptic lineages within the taxon that require integrative revision. Morphologically, the Philippine material agrees with the diagnostic features of *C. crassiforceps*, but remote populations remain undescribed or unavailable for comparison.

The Philippine *C. circumdatus* showed minimal divergence (0.00–1.12%) from other Asian sequences, which is fully consistent with expected intraspecific variation. Similarly, Philippine *C. flaviplumus* clustered with Type C sequences, with divergences of only 0.55–1.12%, confirming their conspecificity. Both species showed stable morphology aligning with previous diagnoses, though in *C. flaviplumus* the Philippine specimens exhibited minor overlap in features between Types A and B.

Taken together, these results highlight the usefulness of K2P divergence thresholds as a first step in delimiting chironomid species, while also emphasizing the need for morphological and geographic corroboration. The high divergence of *K. dilimanensis* supports its description as a new species. Philippine *K. calligaster*, *C. circumdatus*, and *C. flaviplumus* show divergence consistent with conspecificity, while *C. crassiforceps* demonstrates a pattern of geographic structuring: Asian populations align genetically and morphologically, but Pacific populations may represent unrecognized lineages. These findings reinforce that “universal thresholds” cannot be applied rigidly to Chironomidae, and integrative taxonomy remains necessary to resolve cryptic diversity (Pramual *et al.*, 2016; Kang *et al.*, 2022a).

Figure 7. Maximum likelihood (ML) tree of COI sequences from chironomids collected in UP Diliman, with morphologically similar sequences retrieved from BLAST and GenBank.

Table 6. Species included in the Maximum Likelihood (ML) tree with their BOLD and/or GenBank Accession numbers.

SUBFAMILY CHIRONOMINAE				
BOLD accession number	GenBank Accession number	Species name	Country of collection	Life stage
<i>Kiefferulus barbatitarsis</i>				
COTW018-08	N/A	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i> ^a	Thailand	Adult
GBDP44165-19	KP902782.1	<i>Kiefferulus barbatitarsis</i>	China	not mentioned
GBMIN55162-17	KP902781.1	<i>Kiefferulus barbatitarsis</i>	China	not mentioned
<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>				
GBAAW52591-24	PP134820.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	India	Larva
GBDP44094-19	KT212999.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Thailand	Larva
GBDP44096-19	KT213001.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Thailand	Larva
GBDP44098-19	KT213003.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Thailand	Larva
GBDP6672-09	DQ648216.2	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Thailand	Larva
GBMNC517-20	MN934321.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	India	Larva
GBMNC518-20	MN934316.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	India	Larva
GBMNC519-20	MN934263.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	India	Larva
GBMNC520-20	MN934261.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	India	Larva
N/A	MN934178.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	India	Larva
N/A	KY830837.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Pakistan	Larva
GBDP44097-19	KT213002.1	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Thailand	Larva
<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>				
GBDPC334-14	AB838672.1	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	Japan	Adult/larvae mentioned in the study
JCDB077-15	N/A	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	Japan	Adult
CHCHI2621-20	N/A	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	China	Adult
YHJ110-18	MN521277.1	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	China	Adult

YHJ160-18	MN521276.1	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	China	Adult
N/A	MN942976.1	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	China	Adult
JCDB078-15	N/A	<i>Kiefferulus tainanus</i>	Japan	Adult
<i>Chironomus claggi</i>				
GBCAB32700-24	LC773052.1	<i>Chironomus claggi</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBDPC261-14	AB740234.1	<i>Chironomus claggi</i>	Japan	not mentioned
JCDB096-15	N/A	<i>Chironomus claggi</i>	Japan	Adult
JCDB097-15	N/A	<i>Chironomus claggi</i>	Japan	Adult
<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>				
DIQT469-09	"Mined from GenBank, NCBI" - not linked	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Australia	Adult
DIQTB410-11	N/A	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Australia	Adult
DIQTB577-12	N/A	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Australia	Adult
GBDP44141-19	KP902729.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	China	not mentioned
GBDP44148-19	KP902727.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	China	not mentioned
COTW099-20	N/A	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	India	Larva
COTW115-22	N/A	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Indonesia	Larva
GBCAB43109-24	LC773143.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBMNC9597-20	LC495111.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Japan	Larva/Pupa
JCDB294-15	N/A	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Japan	Adult
MOSPK180-22	OP927187.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Pakistan	not mentioned
COTW092-20	ON406921.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Singapore	Larva
GBDP12395-12	JQ287743.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Thailand	Larva
GBDP12396-12	JQ287744.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Thailand	Larva
N/A	OP381679.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	South Korea	Adult
N/A	OM974383.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	South Korea	Adult
N/A	MN934271.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	India	Larva/Pupa

N/A	MN934220.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	India	Larva/Pupa
N/A	KY840786.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Pakistan	not mentioned
N/A	KJ530969.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Singapore	not mentioned
N/A	KJ768129.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Pakistan	not mentioned
COTW090-20	N/A	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	India	Larva
<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i> Type A ^b				
CHCHI2597-20	N/A	Chironomidae gen. sp.	China	Adult
GBCAB2393-24	LC773076	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBCAB2394-24	LC773074.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBCAB2395-24	LC773075.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBCAB2396-24	LC773070.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBDPC246-14	AB740237.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	Adult/Larva
JCDB127-15	N/A	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	Adult
JCDB128-15	N/A	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	Adult
<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i> Type B ^c				
GMBDA028-23	N/A	Chironominae gen. sp.	Bangladesh	Adult
GMBDA066-23	N/A	Chironominae gen. sp.	Bangladesh	Adult
COTW048-11	ON406924.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	India	Larva
COTW107-22	ON406919.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	India	Imago
GBAAW48568-24	PP134822.1	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	India	Larva
GBMNB17168-20	MN370037.1	<i>Chironomus ramosus</i>	India	Larva/Pupa
GBMNC9787-20	LC494841.1	Chironomidae gen. sp.	Japan	not mentioned
GBMNC9788-20	LC494786.1	Chironomidae gen. sp.	Japan	not mentioned

GMMBI822-16	N/A	<i>Chironomus</i> sp.	Malaysia	Adult
MAMOS346-12	N/A	<i>Chironomus incertipenis</i>	Pakistan	Adult
MAMOS347-12	N/A	<i>Chironomus incertipenis</i>	Pakistan	Adult
COTW114-22	ON406926.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Singapore	Larva
<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i> Type C^d				
DIQTB183-10	N/A	<i>Chironomus</i> sp.	Australia	Adult
CHCHI1891-20	N/A	Chironomidae gen. sp.	China	Larva
GBDP44178-19	KP902731.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	China	not mentioned
GBMIN54492-17	KP902730.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	China	not mentioned
GBCAB36314-24	LC773353.1	<i>Chironomus samoensis</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBDP44633-19	LC329049.1	<i>Chironomus samoensis</i>	Japan	not mentioned
<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i> (uncategorized)				
N/A	MN521255.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Brazil	Adult
N/A	MN521254.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Brazil	Adult
N/A	MN521253.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Brazil	Adult
N/A	MN521252.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Brazil	Adult
N/A	MN942988.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	China	Adult
N/A	AB740239.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
N/A	ON406917.1	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Singapore	not mentioned
<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>				
GMBRM895-18	N/A	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	Bangladesh	not mentioned
GBAAW78906-24	PP504874.1	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	India	Adult
GBDP44076-19	KT212978.1	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	Thailand	Larva
GBMIN54491-17	KT212979.1	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	Thailand	Larva
PAL309-19	N/A	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	United States Minor Outlying	Adult

			Islands	
SYC1355-14	KX051998.1	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	French Polynesia	Adult
SYC5336-14	KX051997.1	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	French Polynesia	Adult
COTW030-10	N/A	<i>Chironomus magnivalva</i> ^e	French Polynesia	Larva
CAUS013-09	N/A	<i>Chironomus magnivalva</i> ^e	Australia	Larva
GBDPC073-13	AB769382.1	<i>Chironomus magnivalva</i> ^e	Tuvalu Oceania	Adult
<i>Chironomus samoensis</i>				
COTW056-19	N/A	<i>Chironomus samoensis</i>	American Samoa	Larva
GMRUF125-16	N/A	<i>Chironomus samoensis</i>	Russia	not mentioned
GMRUF218-16	N/A	<i>Chironomus samoensis</i>	Russia	not mentioned
Species from the Philippines				
N/A	PX559725	<i>Kiefferulus dilimanensis</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559726	<i>Kiefferulus dilimanensis</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559727	<i>Kiefferulus dilimanensis</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559728	<i>Kiefferulus dilimanensis</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559730	<i>Kiefferulus calligaster</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559729	<i>Chironomus flaviplumus</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559731	<i>Chironomus crassiforceps</i>	Philippines	Adult
N/A	PX559732	<i>Chironomus circumdatus</i>	Philippines	Adult
SUBFAMILY ORTHOCLADIINAE				
GBCAB29680-24	LC773348.1	<i>Cricotopus triannulatus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBCAB34326-24	LC773425.1	<i>Nanocladius tamabicolor</i>	Japan	not mentioned
SUBFAMILY TANYPODINAE				
GBMNC9768-20	LC494895.1	<i>Procladius choreus</i>	Japan	not mentioned
GBDPC262-14	AB838638.1	<i>Ablabesmyia monilis</i>	Japan	Adult/Larva

a – mentioned as *Kiefferulus barbitarsis* (Martin, 2020)

b – columns of species under this type are categorized as *Chironomus flaviplumus* Type A (Martin, 2020) in BOLD Bin: [BOLD:ACQ8383](#)

c – columns of species under this type are categorized as *Chironomus flaviplumus* Type B (Martin, 2020) in BOLD Bin: [BOLD:AAW3997](#)

d – columns of species under this type are categorized as *Chironomus flaviplumus* Type C (Martin, 2020) in BOLD Bin: [BOLD:AAV5954](https://www.boldsystems.org/#genid:AAV5954)

e – columns of species under this type are categorized as *Chironomus crassiforceps* (Martin, 2020) in BOLD Bin: [BOLD:AAJ4269](https://www.boldsystems.org/#genid:AAJ4269)

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